

THE TRANSLATION OF ARGOT, JARGON AND SLANG IN LITERARY TEXTS: A CASE STUDY OF THE CATCHER IN THE RYE (JAVDARZORDAGI XALOSKOR) WITH A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK VERSIONS

Ziyoda Karimova

Year Student of Translation Studies, Kimyo International University in Tashkent

Xamidova Mohinaxon Alisherovna

KIUT, Translation theory and practice department, associate professor

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20338481>

Abstract. *This article examines one of the actual issues in literary translation, namely argot, jargon and slang units' translation into other languages. It focuses on the challenges of finding adequate equivalents and the possible errors which may occur in the translation process, based on the example of Jerome Salinger's novel The Catcher in the Rye.*

The article is dedicated to the study of the stylistic features of slang units used in the novel. During the research, particular attention is given to their pragmatic functions as elements of informal vocabulary, as well as their role in shaping individual speech. Moreover, the significance of slang in expressing the protagonist's worldview and his attitude toward the social environment is analyzed.

Keywords: *slang, jargon, argot, literary translation, comparative analysis, expressive coloring, stylistic equivalents, colloquial speech, Holden Caulfield,*

One of the major issues in literary translation is the adequate rendering of lexical units that reflect the historical, cultural and social layers of a language. In this respect, argot, jargon and slang units deserve special attention. These units belong to the living layer of language and reflect the speech culture, values and communicative traditions of a particular society.

Moreover, such non-standard lexical units are characterized by their dynamic nature, as they may change their form and meaning over time, develop new usages or even disappear. Therefore, their translation involves several important challenges. Among them are finding appropriate equivalents, preserving stylistic features and accurately conveying the cultural context, all of which directly affect the quality of translation.

Jerome Salinger's *The Catcher in the Rye* is one of the most well-known works of 20th-century American literature, first published in 1951. The novel quickly gained popularity and was especially notable for its unique portrayal of adolescent psychology. It is narrated by the protagonist, Holden Caulfield, whose life, inner experiences and attitude toward society are presented throughout the text.

The relevance of this study is determined by the theoretical and practical importance of identifying and classifying argot, jargon and slang units used in the novel, as well as examining the extent to which the national and cultural coloring is preserved or lost in their translation into Uzbek. The aim of the study is to analyze how non-standard lexical units in the novel are adapted to Uzbek speech culture during the translation process and to what extent the stylistic features of the original text are preserved.

Argot, jargon and slang units are an important part of informal vocabulary in linguistics and actively used in the speech of various social groups. These units are characterized by their distraction from standard language norms, their emotional and expressive nature and their social limitations. Argot is mainly a form of secret language used by closed social groups, such as criminals or individuals involved in illegal activities. The main purpose of such units is creating a communicative environment that is not easily understood by others who do not belong to them. For example, "cop" means a police officer, "snitch" refers to an informer or traitor and "stash" means a hidden item. Jargon also belongs to a restricted layer of vocabulary and is formed within specific professions, social groups or fields of activity. It is usually understood only by members of a particular group. For instance, in the field of information technology, "bug" refers to a software error, while "deadline" means the time limit for completing a task.

Slang differs from these two categories due to its wider use among the general public. According to Eric Partridge, slang is a constantly changing and essential element of informal speech. Moreover, Connie Eble also points out that slang units are mainly formed within youth and social group communication and serve an important identifying function. The term "slang" first appeared in written sources in English in the late 18th and early 19th centuries. Slang is mostly found in youth speech and is used to express emotions and inner experiences. Over time, new forms of slang continue emerging. For example: in the 1940s–1950s, the expression "cool cat" was used to describe a calm and self-confident person, while in modern English its equivalents include "cool guy" or "chill guy." Other examples of slang include "phony" (a hypocritical person), "lousy" (very bad) and "damn" (used as an emotional intensifier).

Research Methodology

1. Corpus Compilation:

Slang units were extracted from the original text of *The Catcher in the Rye*.

2. Classification:

The identified slang items were grouped into the following categories:

CORE HOLDEN SLANG

Phony, lousy, crap, crumby, bastard, moron, jerk, slob, dopey, hotshot, nutty, corny, swell, terrific.

TALKING / BEHAVIOR SLANG

Shoot the bull, shoot the crap, chew the rag, horse around, fool around, kid around, hang around, make cracks, start chucking the old crap, give somebody a buzz, get wise with somebody.

ANGER / EMPHASIS SLANG

What the hell, who the hell, how the hell, as hell, like hell, cold as hell, sore as hell, scared as hell, bored as hell, drunk as hell.

MONEY SLANG

Dough, a buck, a wad, shell out, make dough.

MENTAL / EMOTIONAL SLANG

Go crazy, drive somebody crazy, nuts, lose your marbles, my nerves were shot, feel rotten, feel lousy.

FIGHT / ACTION SLANG

Knock somebody out, beat somebody up, rough somebody up, sock somebody, land on somebody, give a shove, smash somebody.

ACTION / LIFE SLANG

Beat it, clear the hell out, get the hell out, sneak a look, barge in, chuck it, pick it up, drop it, flop, haul in.

CHARACTER TYPE SLANG

Booze hound, crumb-bum, big shot, snob, crook, phony guy, show-off, wise guy.

BODY / DIRTY SLANG

Puke, puke your guts out, snotty, stinking, filthy, ass (used as an insult).

RELATIONSHIP SLANG

Necking, feel horny, pimp, whore (contextual use), screw up (figurative meaning)

RANDOM HOLDEN-STYLE SLANG

Up the creek, kill me (humorous expression), that killed me, get a bang out of, knock me out (to impress), feel swell, pretty lousy, old crap, goddam (intensifier).

3. Comparative Analysis:

The original English version of the novel (*The Catcher in the Rye*, 1951) and its Uzbek translation (Javdarzordagi xaloskor, 2020) by Z.Raximjonova and O'.Miraxmatov were analyzed comparatively.

Example 1: the slang expression “phony” carries a meaning that extends beyond the simple definition of “fake”. As a slang unit, it is used to describe a person or phenomenon perceived as artificial, pretentious and emotionally insincere. The word contains a strong negative evaluative connotation and rejection. However, the Uzbek equivalent “soxta” is comparatively more neutral and literary in tone, whereas the original slang expression possesses a stronger colloquial and emotionally charged character. Alternative renderings such as “yasama”, “ko'zbo'yamachilik” or expressions implying pretentious behavior could preserve the expressive and stylistic intensity of the original more effectively. Consequently, part of the emotional and social coloring embedded in the slang expression “phony” is weakened in translation.

English: Grand. There is a word I really hate. It's a **phony**. (page 5)

Uzbek: Oliyjanob. Bu so'zni o'lgudek yomon ko'raman. **Soxta**. (page 17)

Example 2: in this case, the expression “havo unchalik ham ochiq emasligi uchun” appears less effective in conveying the original stylistic and emotional intensity of the slang adjective “lousy.” Alternative renderings such as “rasvo ob-havo” or “yoqimsiz ob-havo sababli” would have been more appropriate, as they better preserve the negative evaluative coloring and expressive force of the source expression. The chosen translation transfers the general meaning; however, it weakens the vividness and emotional impact characteristic of the original slang usage.

English: There weren't too many people in the zoo because it was sort of **lousy** day, ... (page 112)

Uzbek: **Havo unchalik ham ochiq emasligi uchun** hayvonot bog'ida odam ko'p emasdi. (page 314)

Example 3: The adjective “crumby” contains not only the semantic meaning of inferiority or poor quality, but also a strong emotional and evaluative coloring. Translating it merely as “arzimas” may preserve the idea of insignificance; however, it can weaken the irritation and contempt expressed in the original slang usage. In this context, replacing the translation equivalent “arzimas maktab” with alternatives such as “rasvo maktab” or “jirkanch maktab” would have been more appropriate. These expressions correspond more closely to Holden Caulfield's colloquial manner of speech and more effectively preserve the expressive coloring conveyed in the original slang usage.

English: Her son was doubtless the biggest bastard that ever went to Pencey, in the whole **crumby** history of the school. (page 30)

Uzbek: Shubhasiz, uning o'g'li Pensining butun boshli **arzimas** tarixidagi eng iflos o'quvchi edi. (page 85)

1.Results and Discussion:

A comparative analysis of the English original and the Uzbek translation of *The Catcher in the Rye* demonstrates that preserving the original meaning and expressive coloring of linguistic units such as slang, jargon and argot represents one of the most challenging aspects of the translation process. The study reveals that these non-standard lexical elements often carry not only semantic meaning but also strong emotional, social and stylistic connotations, many of which may be partially weakened or lost in translation.

Essential for translators:

1. Translators must have a deep understanding of the socio-cultural context and historical background in which the original literary work was created.
2. They should possess sufficient practical experience in translating slang and jargon expressions, particularly those reflecting colloquial and emotionally expressive speech.
3. Translators must remain aware of potential lexical inaccuracies and stylistic losses that may arise during the translation process in order to preserve the authenticity and communicative impact of the original text as effectively as possible.

This research has examined the usage of slang terms in *The Catcher in the Rye*, with particular attention to their linguistic and stylistic functions. The analysis demonstrates that slang has not only an informal layer of vocabulary, but also a central element in constructing the narrative style and character identity. Especially, the frequent use of slang by Holden Caulfield reflects his emotional instability, critical attitude toward society and desire for authenticity. Based on these expressions, the novel achieves a high degree of realism, closely resembling natural spoken language, especially, adolescent speech. Additionally, the findings highlight that slang plays a crucial role in conveying tone, attitude and interpersonal dynamics. It serves as a marker of social identity and psychological state of the protagonist and making it an essential feature of the text rather than a peripheral one.

From a translation perspective, the study illustrates the challenges of the integrity, emotional depth and realism of the original work.

REFERENCES

1. Partridge, E. (2002). *Slang: Today and Yesterday*. Routledge.
2. Eble, C. (1996). *Slang and Sociability*. University of North Carolina Press.
3. Salinger, J. D. (1951). *The Catcher in the Rye*. Little, Brown and Company
4. Salinger, J. D. *Javdarzordagi xaloskor*. Translated by Z. Raximova and O'. Miraxmatova, Asaxiy Books, 2020.